

STUDY PLAN AND RESULTS Test Facility Study No. 20335884 Pharmacokinetics of BDT272 Following Oral Administration to Male Beagle Dogs	
Test Facility: Charles River Laboratories Den Bosch Hambakenwetering 7 5231 DD, 's-Hertogenbosch The Netherlands	Sponsor: Biodol Therapeutics CAP Alpha 9 Avenue De l'Europe 34830 Clapiers France
Study Director: Coordinating Biotechnician: Handling of blood samples: Individual Scientist Bioanalysis: Individual Scientist Pharmacokinetic Evaluation:	Freeke van Pijpen Koen van der Meijde Paula Polman Harold Darwinkel Mirelle Engels
Sponsor Representative:	Pierre Sokoloff Tel: +33 7 70 41 63 68 E-mail: pierre.sokoloff@biodol.eu
Test Facility Study No:	20335884
Compliance:	Not claiming GLP compliance
Projected Dosing Date: Dosing End of In-life: Experimental Completion Date: Proposed Sample Shipment Date:	11 Nov 2021 19 Nov 2021 06 Jan 2022 22 Nov 2021 The Bioanalytical study will be performed at the Groningen location, all other supporting activities will be performed at the 's-Hertogenbosch location.
Study Objective:	To determine the intrinsic pharmacokinetics of the test compounds when given orally to male Beagle dogs.
Test System:	Dog: Beagle dog, Pure bred, Marshall BioResources, 5800 Lake Bluff Rd, North Rose, New York 14516, USA. The animals (3 males) will be between 1.5 to 2 years old with a target body weight ranging between 8 to 11 kg at dosing. The animals were last used in Test Facility Study No. 20241158. Animals were not used after 27 Jul 2021.
Guidelines and Animal Welfare	At this time, studies in laboratory animals provide the best available basis for extrapolation to humans and are required to support regulatory submissions. Acceptable models that do not use live animals currently do not exist. The Beagle dog was chosen as the animal model for this study as it is an accepted nonrodent species for nonclinical toxicity test by regulatory agencies. The total number of animals to be used in this study is considered to be the minimum required to properly characterize the effects of the test item and has been designed such that it does not require an unnecessary number of animals to accomplish its objectives. There are no applicable guidelines for the conduct of this screening study.

	This Study Plan was reviewed and agreed by the Animal Welfare Body of Charles River Laboratories Den Bosch B.V. within the framework of Appendix 2 of project license AVD2360020173904 approved by the Central Authority for Scientific Procedures on Animals (CCD) as required by the Dutch Act on Animal Experimentation (December 2014).					
Animal Housing and Husbandry:	<p>Animals will be socially housed per group of up to 3 animals in anodized aluminum or stainless steel cages and sterilized Corncob will be used as bedding material, unless contraindicated by study procedures (such as toxicokinetic blood sampling) or clinical signs. Water will be freely available to each animal via an automatic watering system (except during designated procedures).</p> <p>For psychological/environmental enrichment, animals will be provided with items such as balls, except when interrupted by study procedures/activities. Veterinary care will be available throughout the course of the study</p> <p>On dosing days, animals will be individually housed for approximately 2 hours directly after dosing and will be pair-housed thereafter.</p> <p>Hd-H, Extrudat (SSNIFF® Spezialdiäten GmbH, Soest, Germany) pelleted diet for dogs will be used. On non-dosing days, animals will be offered once daily 0.150-0.350 kg/animal/day for a period of approximately 2 to 4 hours. Any remaining diet after that period will be discarded. During food consumption, animals may be housed individually, if necessary.</p> <p>During the night prior to dosing, the animals will be fasted (at minimum 12 hours), but water will be available. Food will be available approximately 2 hours after dosing.</p>					
Test Item(s):	BDT272 (213138/A)					
Dose Vehicle(s):	7% Tween80 in 0.9% NaCl					
Dose Formulation Preparation:	<p>The dose formulations will be prepared on the day of dose administration.</p> <p>The test items will be dissolved in the vehicle to meet dose level requirements. The formulations will be stirred, vortexed and/or sonicated to obtain a homogeneous formulation.</p> <p>Any residual volumes will be discarded unless otherwise requested by the Study Director.</p>					
Study Design:						
Period¹	Test Item Name¹	Route of administration	Dose level mg/kg²	Dose volume mL/kg	Number of Animals	Animal Numbers
					Males	Males
1	BDT272	po by oral gavage	5	5	3	1-3
¹ Test items are intended to be used as the treatment of pain disorders;						
² The dose are relatively low and chosen to minimise the prospect achieving any potential on target / off target toxicity and of achieving non-linear PK as a consequence of saturation of in vivo drug metabolism pathways.						
Treatment:	<p>Oral gavage using a flexible catheter.</p> <p>During the night prior to treatment, the animals will be deprived of food, but water will be available. Food will be available approximately 2 hours after dosing.</p>					
Observations:	BW prior to dosing.					

	<p>Clinical signs during dosing and sample collection period.</p> <p>Animals showing pain, distress or discomfort which is considered not transient in nature or is likely to become more severe, will be sacrificed for humane reasons based on OECD guidance document on humane endpoints (ENV/JM/MONO/ 2000/7). The circumstances of any death will be recorded in detail.</p> <p>(Test Facility Study No. for Toxdata (in-life phase): 523399)</p>
Bioanalytical Sample Collection:	<p>From all animals approximately 1 mL blood samples will be taken from the jugular vein using K₂-EDTA as anticoagulant. Blood samples will be collected at the following time points: 30 min (0.5h), 1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 8 and 24 hours after dosing.</p> <p>Blood will be kept on ice. Samples will be centrifuged within 1 hour after blood sampling at approximately 2000g for 10 minutes at 2-8°C. Immediately after centrifugation, plasma will be stored in labeled polypropylene tubes in an ultra-low freezer set to maintain -80°C until shipped on dry ice to the bioanalysis group.</p>
Bioanalysis:	<p>Plasma samples will be analyzed for the concentration of BDT272 using a non-GLP RGA Level 2 analytical procedure. Key 2371C will be used for study identification and data reporting. Any residual/retained bioanalytical samples will be discarded upon authorization by the Study Director.</p>
Pharmacokinetic Evaluation:	<p>Pharmacokinetic parameters will be calculated from the individual curves, using the Phoenix WinNonlin 6.4 program. Non-compartmental analysis with the oral route of administration will be applied. All parameters will be generated from BDT272 individual concentrations in plasma. Individual values below the LLOQ will be taken as zero in calculating the descriptive statistics.</p> <p>Parameters to be calculated are (if data allow): C_{max}, and t_{max}, t_{last}, AUC_{last}, AUC_∞, λ_z, and t_{1/2}.</p>
Terminal Procedure	<p>Animals will not be subjected to necropsy, and will be returned to the Test Facility animal pool.</p>
Reporting:	<p>QC-checked Bioanalytical Results (Excel sheet): 10 Dec 2021 QC-checked Pharmacokinetic Evaluation Results (Excel sheet): 24 Dec 2021 In-life Results (Excel sheet): 24 Dec 2021</p>
Archiving:	<p>Two years following issuance of the tabulated data.</p>
Study Plan Approved By: Freeke van Pijpen, MSc Study Director, Charles River	<p>All electronic signatures appear at the end of the document upon finalization.</p>
Study Plan Approved By: Pierre Sokoloff Sponsor Representative, Biodol Therapeutics	<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-between; align-items: flex-end;"> <div style="text-align: center;"> Signature </div> <div style="text-align: right;"> 02 November, 2021 Date </div> </div>

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SIGNATURE(S) FOR DOCUMENT: 20335884 - Study Plan Final

Study Director Approval:	I approve this document.	
Name:	van Pijpen, Freeke	
	<i>van Pijpen Freeke</i>	
		08-Nov-2021 17:31:29 (UTC+00:00)
Electronically Signed in		Timestamp

RESULTS

CRL Project 20335884															
Test Item:															
Test Item Identification		Test Item Number													
BDT272		213138/A													
Test System:															
Beagle dog: Pure bred, Marshall BioResources, 5800 Lake Bluff Rd, North Rose, New York, 14516, USA.															
Study Design:															
Test Item Name		Route of administration		Dose level (mg/kg)		Dose volume (mL/kg)		Number of Animals		Animal Numbers					
								Males		Males					
BDT272		po by oral gavage		5		5		3		1-3					
PK Sample Collection Schedule:															
PK Sample Collection Schedule (Time Postdose)															
0.5h		1h		2h		3h		4h		6h		8h		24h	
Subject numbers															
1-3		1-3		1-3		1-3		1-3		1-3		1-3			
Approximately 1 mL blood was collected according to the PK Sample Collection Table via the jugular vein using K ₂ -EDTA as anticoagulant. Animals were not subjected to necropsy.															
Vehicle:															
7% Tween80 in 0.9% NaCl															
Formulation:															
227 mL of vehicle (7% Tween80 in 0.9% NaCl) was added to 226.75 mg test item (213138/A3). The test item was dissolved by stirring for 15 minutes and sonicating for 15 minutes. The final formulation was a brown, homogenous suspension, which was kept under continuous stirring at room temperature until dosing.															
Clinical Observations:															
No clinical signs were noted.															
See attached PDF scan.															
Body weight and dose volume:															
See attached PDF scan.															
Sample Collection Details															
All samples were collected on the planned sampling time, with the exception of:															
Animal No.		Nominal Sampling Time (h)		Actual Sampling Time (h)											
1		0.5		0.52											

1	4	4.02						
1	6	6.02						
1	24	24.7						
2	24	24.7						
3	1	1.02						
3	24	24.6						
No hemolytic plasma samples were present.								
Deviations:								
No deviations occurred during this study.								

Raw data

Period	Animal no	Time point (hr)	Matrix	Concentration (ng/mL)
				BDT272
1	1	0.5	Plasma	51.090
1	2	0.5	Plasma	149.800
1	3	0.5	Plasma	70.570
1	1	1	Plasma	109.500
1	2	1	Plasma	246.200
1	3	1	Plasma	227.500
1	1	2	Plasma	274.400
1	2	2	Plasma	262.600
1	3	2	Plasma	283.300
1	1	3	Plasma	233.700
1	2	3	Plasma	200.500
1	3	3	Plasma	231.100
1	1	4	Plasma	154.900
1	2	4	Plasma	178.100
1	3	4	Plasma	203.200
1	1	6	Plasma	147.700
1	2	6	Plasma	195.800
1	3	6	Plasma	168.700
1	1	8	Plasma	141.200
1	2	8	Plasma	182.500
1	3	8	Plasma	123.300
1	1	24	Plasma	9.582
1	2	24	Plasma	16.060
1	3	24	Plasma	24.840
2	1	0.5	Plasma	NR

LLOQ of BDT272 in plasma: 1 ng/mL

20335884 PK table

Analyte		BDT272					
Dose Level (mg/kg)		5					
Animal		1	2	3	Mean	SD	CV%
t _{last}	h	24	24	24	24	n/a	n/a
t _{max}	h	2	2	2	2	n/a	n/a
C _{max}	ng/mL	274	263	283	273	10.4	4
C _{max} /Dose	kg·ng/mL/mg	54.9	52.5	56.7	54.7	2.08	4
AUC _{last}	h·ng/mL	2490	3150	2670	2770	342	12
AUC _{last} /Dose	h·kg·ng/mL/mg	498	630	534	554	68.4	12
AUC _∞	h·ng/mL	2550	3260	2910	2910	356	12
AUC _∞ /Dose	h·kg·ng/mL/mg	510	653	581	581	71.2	12
%extrapolated	%	2	3	8	n/a	n/a	n/a
λ _z	1/h	0.158	0.144	0.106	0.136	0.0272	20
t _{1/2}	h	4.38	4.82	6.57	5.26	1.16	22
No. of points		3	3	5	n/a	n/a	n/a
r ²		0.9924	0.9941	0.9978	n/a	n/a	n/a

n/a: not applicable.

GRAPH

1.1 CLINICAL SIGNS
MALES

(LOCATION)	SIGN (MAX. GRADE)		WEEK:
	1.	1.	1.
	DAY: 12	12	
GROUP 1 (GROUP 1) ANIMAL 1			
No clinical signs noted			
ANIMAL 2			
No clinical signs noted			
ANIMAL 3			
No clinical signs noted			

.: Observation performed, sign not present

24Nov21 12h37

BDT272
APPENDIX 1

523399 Project 20335884

1.2 BODY WEIGHTS (KG)
MALES

	PERIOD 1
DAYS	1
WEEKS	1
ANIMAL	

GROUP 1 (GROUP 1)

1	8.9
2	9.8
3	9.0

24Nov21 12h37

APPLIKATIONSMENGEN VOM 11-NOV-21 (PO)

Tier	Sex	Gr.	Applikationsmenge [ML]	Körpergewicht [g]	Phase/Tag	Dosis [MG/KG]	Volumen/KG [ML]
1	M	1	45	8920	1 / 1	5	5
2	M	1	49	9760	1 / 1	5	5
3	M	1	45	8960	1 / 1	5	5

geprint door: DyJ 11nov2021

doseer volume geldig voor 11nov2021 DyJ 11nov2021

gedoseerd door: DII 11nov2021 ①

gechecked door: DyJ 11nov2021

① in training DII 11nov2021

APPLIKATIONSMENGEN VOM 18-NOV-21 (PO)

Tier	Sex	Gr.	Applikationsmenge [ML]	Körpergewicht [g]	Phase/Tag	Dosis [MG/KG]	Volumen/KG [ML]
1	M	1	44	8880	2 / 1	5	5
2	M	1	48	9580	2 / 1	5	5
3	M	1	46	9240	2 / 1	5	5

geprint door D4J18nov2021

doseer volume geldig voor 18nov2021 - D4J18nov2021

gedoseerd door: D4J18nov2021

gechecked door: H.m 18 nov 2021